

SM3.1. The socio-economic consequences of switching from specialised to mixed crop-livestock farming in Europe – Supplementary materials

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S1. Expanded summary statistics

Table S1.1. Summary statistics by farm-year for the FADN sample

Dependent variable	Observations	Min	Max	Median	Mean	Std. dev.
<i>All farms</i> 1,124,088						
Unpaid labour hours (h)		0	8,168	2,722	2,933	1,504
Wages paid (€)		0	532,375	0	12,154	39,311
Revenues (€)	2,898	2,590,646	62,516	140,174	212,204	
Crop revenues (€)	0	1,455,276	23,568	71,350	139,355	
Livestock revenues (€)	0	1,323,982	6,552	61,464	136,385	
Variable costs (€)	1,487	1,746,223	36,450	88,411	144,308	
Farm net profits (€)	-121,928	450,434	18,781	34,419	54,056	
Economic productivity (€)	-1,422,194	2,589,631	33,737	78,547	128,747	
<i>Specialised crop</i> 531,696						
Unpaid labour hours (h)		0	8,168	2,232	2,538	1,444
Wages paid (€)		0	531,554	1,000	15,454	41,678
Revenues (€)	2,898	2,535,318	52,401	125,185	196,289	
Crop revenues (€)	0	1,455,276	48,474	114,216	177,156	
Livestock revenues (€)	0	1,255,615	0	2,705	22,262	
Variable costs (€)	1,487	1,743,845	25,732	67,432	116,138	
Farm net profits (€)	-121,927	450,434	17,677	35,164	57,719	
Economic productivity (€)	-1,422,194	2,589,631	35,852	90,839	150,208	
<i>Specialised livestock</i> 468,199						
Unpaid labour hours (h)		0	8,168	3,200	3,312	1,463
Wages paid (€)		0	531,415	0	8,199	30,833
Revenues (€)	2,899	2,590,646	79,983	158,297	216,819	
Crop revenues (€)	0	1,406,753	9,128	24,303	48,668	
Livestock revenues (€)	0	1,323,982	61,694	127,831	178,624	
Variable costs (€)	1,487	1,739,442	53,361	110,483	157,866	
Farm net profits (€)	-121,928	450,356	22,018	35,530	51,019	
Economic productivity (€)	-1,220,993	1,789,024	33,907	67,018	97,598	
<i>Mixed crop-livestock</i> 124,193						
Unpaid labour hours (h)		0	8,165	3,143	3,194	1,480
Wages paid (€)		0	532,375	0	12,936	53,484
Revenues (€)	2,898	2,576,578	46,764	136,022	251,358	

Crop revenues (€)	0	1,452,999	22,681	65,194	127,403
Livestock revenues (€)	0	1,313,127	19,265	62,822	120,679
Variable costs (€)	1,487	1,746,223	31,017	95,015	181,731
Farm net profits (€)	-121,830	447,845	12,507	27,044	48,076
Economic productivity (€)	-1,235,338	2,036,812	24,923	69,388	127,648

Table S1.2. Numbers of distinct farm holdings and switchers by country

Country	Total distinct IDs		Distinct crop switcher IDs			Distinct livestock switcher IDs		
	Country total	% of total EU28	#	% of total switchers	% of country	#	% of total switchers	% of country
Austria	3,639	1.77%	13	1.26%	0.36%	126	2.79%	3.46%
Belgium	2,299	1.12%	14	1.35%	0.61%	51	1.13%	2.22%
Bulgaria	5,130	2.50%	17	1.64%	0.33%	28	0.62%	0.55%
Croatia	1,746	0.85%	16	1.55%	0.92%	20	0.44%	1.15%
Cyprus	1,428	0.70%	4	0.39%	0.28%	4	0.09%	0.28%
Czechia	2,892	1.41%	40	3.86%	1.38%	60	1.33%	2.07%
Denmark	6,637	3.24%	7	0.68%	0.11%	27	0.60%	0.41%
Estonia	1,209	0.59%	3	0.29%	0.25%	51	1.13%	4.22%
Finland	1,533	0.75%	2	0.19%	0.13%	35	0.78%	2.28%
France	17,003	8.29%	93	8.99%	0.55%	314	6.96%	1.85%
Germany	18,684	9.11%	82	7.92%	0.44%	506	11.21%	2.71%
Greece	8,238	4.02%	124	11.98%	1.51%	92	2.04%	1.12%
Hungary	3,770	1.84%	51	4.93%	1.35%	107	2.37%	2.84%
Ireland	2,017	0.98%	13	1.26%	0.64%	25	0.55%	1.24%
Italy	38,413	18.73%	110	10.63%	0.29%	180	3.99%	0.47%
Latvia	2,096	1.02%	21	2.03%	1.00%	77	1.71%	3.67%
Lithuania	4,214	2.05%	9	0.87%	0.21%	34	0.75%	0.81%
Luxembourg	861	0.42%	3	0.29%	0.35%	16	0.35%	1.86%
Malta	929	0.45%	4	0.39%	0.43%	3	0.07%	0.32%
Netherlands	2,581	1.26%	5	0.48%	0.19%	12	0.27%	0.46%
Poland	28,264	13.78%	198	19.13%	0.70%	2,227	49.35%	7.88%
Portugal	4,789	2.34%	24	2.32%	0.50%	46	1.02%	0.96%
Romania	16,783	8.18%	56	5.41%	0.33%	106	2.35%	0.63%
Slovakia	1,156	0.56%	6	0.58%	0.52%	13	0.29%	1.12%
Slovenia	2,380	1.16%	5	0.48%	0.21%	42	0.93%	1.76%
Spain	17,992	8.77%	71	6.86%	0.39%	209	4.63%	1.16%
Sweden	2,063	1.01%	6	0.58%	0.29%	60	1.33%	2.91%
United Kingdom	6,325	3.08%	38	3.67%	0.60%	42	0.93%	0.66%
TOTAL EU28	205,071	100%	1,035	100%	0.50%	4,513	100%	2.20%

Table S1.3. Number of farm-year observations by farming type and country

Country	Total farm-year observations		Farm-year observations = specialised cropping			Farm-year observations = specialised livestock			Farm-year observations = mixed crop-livestock		
	Country total	% of total EU28	#	% of total s. crop.	% of country	#	% of total s. live.	% of country	#	% of total mixed	% of country
Austria	29,929	2.66%	7,841	1.47%	26.20%	19,898	4.25%	66.48%	2,190	1.76%	7.32%
Belgium	16,365	1.46%	4,741	0.89%	28.97%	9,625	2.06%	58.81%	1,999	1.61%	12.22%
Bulgaria	20,988	1.87%	12,621	2.37%	60.13%	6,503	1.39%	30.98%	1,864	1.50%	8.88%
Croatia	7,028	0.63%	2,892	0.54%	41.15%	3,007	0.64%	42.79%	1,129	0.91%	16.06%
Cyprus	5,499	0.49%	4,004	0.75%	72.81%	1,288	0.28%	23.42%	207	0.17%	3.76%
Czechia	16,030	1.43%	7,610	1.43%	47.47%	5,149	1.10%	32.12%	3,271	2.63%	20.41%
Denmark	21,395	1.90%	8,849	1.66%	41.36%	10,333	2.21%	48.30%	2,213	1.78%	10.34%
Estonia	7,910	0.70%	3,107	0.58%	39.28%	3,795	0.81%	47.98%	1,008	0.81%	12.74%
Finland	12,193	1.08%	4,494	0.85%	36.86%	7,130	1.52%	58.48%	569	0.46%	4.67%
France	107,535	9.57%	52,584	9.89%	48.90%	44,670	9.54%	41.54%	10,281	8.28%	9.56%
Germany	118,707	10.56%	41,855	7.87%	35.26%	61,204	13.07%	51.56%	15,648	12.60%	13.18%
Greece	56,296	5.01%	43,435	8.17%	77.15%	8,470	1.81%	15.05%	4,391	3.54%	7.80%
Hungary	27,537	2.45%	18,865	3.55%	68.51%	5,530	1.18%	20.08%	3,142	2.53%	11.41%
Ireland	13,746	1.22%	675	0.13%	4.91%	12,357	2.64%	89.90%	714	0.57%	5.19%
Italy	158,207	14.07%	107,755	20.27%	68.11%	42,745	9.13%	27.02%	7,707	6.21%	4.87%
Latvia	13,858	1.23%	4,943	0.93%	35.67%	6,759	1.44%	48.77%	2,156	1.74%	15.56%
Lithuania	15,884	1.41%	7,663	1.44%	48.24%	5,257	1.12%	33.10%	2,964	2.39%	18.66%
Luxembourg	6,517	0.58%	504	0.09%	7.73%	5,643	1.21%	86.59%	370	0.30%	5.68%
Malta	5,488	0.49%	2,906	0.55%	52.95%	2,406	0.51%	43.84%	176	0.14%	3.21%
Netherlands	18,069	1.61%	8,339	1.57%	46.15%	9,335	1.99%	51.66%	395	0.32%	2.19%
Poland	173,373	15.42%	55,225	10.39%	31.85%	76,019	16.24%	43.85%	42,129	33.92%	24.30%
Portugal	28,603	2.54%	12,827	2.41%	44.84%	13,942	2.98%	48.74%	1,834	1.48%	6.41%
Romania	47,279	4.21%	26,056	4.90%	55.11%	14,486	3.09%	30.64%	6,737	5.42%	14.25%
Slovakia	5,349	0.48%	3,193	0.60%	59.69%	1,398	0.30%	26.14%	758	0.61%	14.17%
Slovenia	11,968	1.06%	2,052	0.39%	17.15%	8,341	1.78%	69.69%	1,575	1.27%	13.16%
Spain	124,688	11.09%	73,749	13.87%	59.15%	46,606	9.95%	37.38%	4,333	3.49%	3.48%
Sweden	14,522	1.29%	3,014	0.57%	20.75%	10,569	2.26%	72.78%	939	0.76%	6.47%
United Kingdom	39,125	3.48%	9,897	1.86%	25.30%	25,734	5.50%	65.77%	3,494	2.81%	8.93%
TOTAL EU28	1,124,088	100%	531,696	100%	47.30%	468,199	100%	41.65%	124,193	100%	11.05%

S2. Results

S2A. Main results – Baseline *csdid*

In order to obtain the event-study-type plots in Figure 1 in the main paper, we use the *csdid* command in Stata to identify the $ATT(g, t)$ s as shown in equation 5 in the main paper and subsequently estimate the aggregated ATT s.

To use the *csdid* command, we input the variables of interest: SE016, unpaid labour hours; SE131, total revenues; SE135, crop revenues; SE206, livestock revenues; SE275, variable costs; SE370, wages paid; SE420, farm net profits; and BLOWE, the Bennet-Lowe indicator of economic productivity. We then define the panel identifier (farm holding ID); and time identifier (YEAR). The group variable identifying the treatment group is defined (treatyear_k). The values of k, 1 and 2, determine whether a farm unit belongs to the group that either switched from specialised cropping of specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming, respectively. This group variable observes the value (the year) in which the farm unit received the treatment. If a farm has never switched, the observed value is equal to 0. We cluster at the NUTS2 level (nomenclature of territorial units for statistics), and estimate the $ATT(g, t)$ s using ordinary least squares regression at the 99% confidence level.

The command itself is as follows:

```
local vars "SE016 SE131 SE135 SE206 SE275 SE370 SE420 BLOWE"  
forvalues k = 1(1)2 {  
  foreach v of local vars {  
    csdid `v',      ivar(ID)      time(YEAR)      gvar(treatyear_`k')  
      cluster(NUTS2_cat) method(reg) level(99)  
    estat simple, level(99)  
    estat group, level(99)  
    estat calendar, level(99)  
    estat event, level(99)
```

```

csdid_plot
graph save `C:\DIRECTORY\OUTPUT_trant\eventplot_`v'`k'.gph"',
    replace
}
}

```

The output report shows the estimated $ATT(g, t)$ s. The table produced by *csdid* is divided by treatment group, and subsequently the effects of the treatment on that group at different periods of time. The reference period is always $t = g - \delta - 1$. Thus, each $ATT(g, t)$ can be interpreted as the effect of the treatment of switching on the farms that switch in period g , at time t .

We produce several summary aggregations. First, a simple, average of all identified $ATT(g, t)$ s. Second, the average effect of group g participating in the treatment, and the overall average of those group averages. In effect, the overall average of group averages is most similar in interpretation to the ATT estimate in classic two-group/two-periods difference-in-differences, and is a useful summary measure of the overall effect of participating in the treatment since groups do not change in composition (ensuring, moreover, that the estimate is free from unwanted weighting biases arising from changes to group sizes). Third, the average effect across time periods, and the overall average across all time periods. Fourth and last, is the average effect of participating in the treatment relative to when the treatment is received. Most importantly, the results that are plotted in the event-study-type plots of Figure 1 are based on these estimates. The average of averages is split into pre-treatment and post-treatment averages.

The order of the results is: 1) the consequences of switching to mixed crop-livestock farming on specialised crop farms on SE016, unpaid labour hours; SE131, total revenues; SE135, crop revenues; SE206, livestock revenues; SE275, variable costs; SE370, wages paid; SE420, farm net profits; and BLOWE, the Bennet-Lowe indicator of economic productivity; 2) the consequences of switching to mixed crop-livestock farming on specialised livestock farms on SE016, unpaid labour hours; SE131, revenues; SE135, crop revenues; SE206, livestock revenues; SE275, variable costs; SE275, variable costs; SE370, wages paid; SE420, farm net profits; and BLOWE, the Bennet-Lowe indicator of economic productivity.

The PDF of the Stata output report containing the results we use in the paper, and based on which the plots are produced, can be found as a supplementary file “SM3.2A – Baseline.pdf”. The complete code can also be found in the supplementary file “SM3.3 – Stata_Code”.

S2B. Sensitivities

S2B1. Description of results

In this iteration of the results, we run the various sensitivity analyses described in section 4.3: 2-period (year) anticipation, more conservative switch conditions, no unswitching, and using the not-yet-treated as the control. In general we find that the estimated aggregated *ATT*s are extremely similar to the baseline *csdid* model.

S2B2. Stata output

The PDFs of the Stata output reports containing the results on which the plots below are produced, can be found as a supplementary files: “SM3.2B1 – Anticipation.pdf”; “SM3.2B2 – Conservative.pdf”; “SM3.2B3 – No_switchbacks.pdf”; “SM3.2B4 – Not-yet-treated.pdf”. The complete code can also be found in the supplementary file “SM3.3 – Stata_Code”.

S2B3. Figures

Figure S2B3.1. CSDID sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on unpaid labour hours

Figure S2B3.2. CSDID sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on unpaid labour hours

Figure S2B3.3. *CSDID* sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on wages paid

Figure S2B3.4. CSDID sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on wages paid

Figure S2B3.5. CSDID sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on crop revenues

Figure S2B3.6. *CSDID* sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on crop revenues

Figure S2B3.7. CSDID sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on livestock revenues

Figure S2B3.8. CSDID sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on livestock revenues

Figure S2B3.9. *CSDID* sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on total revenues

Figure S2B3.10. *CSDID* sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on total revenues

Figure S2B3.11. CSDID sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on variable costs

Figure S2B3.12. *CSDID* sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on variable costs

Figure S2B3.13. CSDID sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on farm net profits

Figure S2B3.14. *CSDID* sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on farm net profits

Figure S2B3.15.: *CSDID* sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on economic productivity

Figure S2B3.16: CSDID sensitivity analysis – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on economic productivity

S2C. Robustness checks – More estimation models

S2C1. Description of results

In this iteration of the results, we run the additional estimation models described in section 4.3: a basic two-way fixed effects model, Sun and Abraham’s *eventstudyinteract* (2021), de Chaisemartin and D’Haultfœuille’s *did_multiplegt_dyn* (2023b; de Chaisemartin et al., 2024), and Borusyak et al.’s *did_imputation* (2024). For all estimation models we estimate confidence intervals at the 99% level, except for *eventstudyinteract* which hard-sets the confidence level at only 95%. In general, we find that the estimated event-study-type models are quite different from the baseline *csdid* model. This would suggest that the assumptions underpinning the different models, particularly parallel-trends, impose these different results.

S2C2. Stata output

The PDFs of the Stata output reports containing the results on which the plots below are produced, can be found as a supplementary files: “SM3.2C1 – TWFE.pdf”; “SM3.2C2 – S&A.pdf”; “SM3.2C3 – dCDH.pdf”; “SM3.2C4 – BJS.pdf”. The complete code can also be found in the supplementary file “SM3.3 – Stata_Code”.

S2C3. Figures

Figure S2C3.1. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on unpaid labour hours

Figure S2C3.2 More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on unpaid labour hours

Figure S2C3.3. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on wages paid

Figure S2C3.4. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on wages paid

Figure S2C3.5. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on crop revenues

Figure S2C3.6. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on crop revenues

Figure S2C3.7. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on livestock revenues

Figure S2C3.8. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on livestock revenues

Figure S2C3.9. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on total revenues

Figure S2C3.10. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on total revenues

Figure S2C3.11. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on variable costs

Figure S2C3.12. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on variable costs

Figure S2C3.13. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on farm net profits

Figure S2C3.14. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on farm net profits

Figure S2C3.15. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised cropping to mixed crop-livestock farming on economic productivity

Figure S2C3.16. More estimation models – Comparing event-study-type plots on the consequence of switching from specialised livestock to mixed crop-livestock farming on economic productivity